

RONGSOKANKU.COM AS A SOLUTION TO REDUCE WASTE AND IMPROVE THE WELFARE OF SOCIETY

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Abstract

Garbage has become a thorny issue in various parts of the world, including Indonesia, Surabaya is one of the largest cities in Indonesia. Based on the data of the Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) in 2016 the production of the most trash was on the island of Java, such as Surabaya. In the year 2015 production waste in Surabaya of 9,475.21 cubic meters and increased to 9,710.61 cubic meters in the year 2016. In addition, the plastic garbages are one of cannot be thrown away and already bad for the environment. The plastic usually ends up in the sea and polluting the sea. This causes health risks for animals and also affecting in our food chain and could end up in food that we consume. The purpose of this writing is to resolve the waste problem faced by Indonesia currently by transforming waste into items of value economically through the website rongsokanku.com. rongsokanku.com also be educational media for society to be able to manage their waste independently and marketing it online. The application of this website can be used as a solution to increasing awareness of the dangers of plastic waste and also can generate profit for society. This paper is based on library research presented in descriptive tabulation and supported by some of the literature relevant to the problems examined. Data processing technique and descriptive analysis. The application of rongsokanku.com website can be used as a solution to reduce waste and improve the welfare of society.

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1. Introduction

The environment is the unity spaces with all objects, resources, circumstances, and living creatures, including humans and behavior that affect human life and well-being of humanism and other living beings (KBBI). In the measurement of the level of health of a community environmental factors occupy the topmost percentage of 45 percent, 30 percent behavior factor, 20 percent of the waiter factor, health and genetic factors only by 5 percent (Hapsari, 2013). Waste becomes a classic problem in Indonesia. According to law No. 18-year 2008 litter is the rest of the everyday activities of humans and/or natural processes that shaped solid. According to (Purwaningrum, 2016) composition of the largest garbage landfill in addition to 70 percent organic waste there is non-organic rubbish that is plastic waste amounted to 14 percent. The estimated amount of garbage continues to grow in Indonesia in 2019 by reaching 68 million tons of trash, and plastic waste is expected to reach 9.52 million tons. In addition, the classification of waste in General, the waste may be classified specifically. Surabaya for example, the amount of garbage is not proportional to the number of the available landfill. As a result, the garbage

build up does not completely out at the corners of the city. The average rate of household garbage in the subdistrict of Sukolilo Surabaya is 0.38 kg/person in a day with the composition of the waste is dominated by the trash can be composted, plastic, and paper. The density of household garbage in the Sukolilo Sub (Surabaya) is 146.02 kg/m³ (Hapsari and Harimurti, 2017). Governments city of Surabaya formed a community Waste Bank for waste management efforts in the city. There is nine Waste Bank in Surabaya which has customer more than 500 people and reaches a turnover amounting to Rp72 million per month (Tanuwijaya, 2016). In addition, the city of Surabaya was already holding large programs are themed health and hygiene. Surabaya green and clean is one program that invites all citizens of Surabaya to participate in waste management and creating a livable environment (Kumalasari, 2015). With the various efforts to create a clean environment, Surabaya is not fully independent of the impact posed by the waste. These problems of pollution, health, and beauty (aesthetics). In addition to the environmental pollution of garbage also health badly. 53.33% of the living surroundings landfill suffered health problems during his stay in the landfill environment. Disorders that often felt was diarrhea, respiratory, and dizziness (Fidiawati and Sudarmaji, 2014). Waste is potentially giving effect to health is B3 garbage, hazardous materials and toxic. 3B is a waste such as batteries, lamps, electricity, electronics, packaging of pesticides, bleach clothing, floor cleaners, paints, and the rest of the drugs (Iswanto, 2016). Most of the garbage (94%) are managed by way of on-site (hoarded or burned on the yard) and the rest is dumped in rivers or the vacant lot (Setiadi, 2015).

The role of the Waste Bank and creative industries are made of garbage still has problems in marketing activities. The emergence of E-commerce makes the give solutions in waste management with effective and efficient. In addition, the sophistication of information technologies is accelerated in an attempt to waste management. Based on the above exposure than needed a concept of empowerment of the economy and the maintenance of the environment. It needs for renewal that is realized through a touch of heart culminate in creative and innovative action. There are the existence of Waste Bank and recycling, so it is a small gap that can be magnified through the action of the visionary. It looks objective and realistic, as it would complement the capabilities of the resource Waste Bank that can synergize with the idea of Rongsokanku.com.

The research problems: How can the mechanism the Waste Bank for waste management in Surabaya? Why urgent Rongsokanku.com applied for the Waste Bank in Surabaya city to enhance the well-being of the community?

2. Theoretical

2.1 Understanding of waste

Trash is all waste generated by human activity and animal-shaped solid sludge, liquid or gas that is discarded because it is unneeded or unwanted again. Although considered useless and undesirable, but sometimes these materials can still be utilized again and made raw materials (Padmi and Damanhuri, 2010). Based on the 1945 Constitution article 1 Garbage is the everyday activities of humans and/or natural processes that shaped solid (bphn.go.id).

2.2 Types of Waste

According to the (fadmi and Damanhuri, 2010), there are some activities that lead to the existence of a source of waste in the industrialized countries, this type of trash or deemed a kind of garbage, grouped by the source as the rubbish settlement. The type of garbage that caused, among others, food scraps, paper, cardboard, plastics, textiles, leather, wood, garden waste, glass, metal, second-hand household hazardous waste, and so on. Second litter from a commercial area that includes shops, restaurants, markets, offices, hotels, and more. The type of garbage that caused, among others, paper, cardboard, plastic, wood, food, glass, metal, toxic and hazardous waste, and so on. Therefore the garbage from institutions i.e. schools, hospitals, prisons, the seat of Government. The types of waste that posed the same as the type of the garbage in the commercial area. In addition to the trash of everyday activities

by turns out development projects also produce waste that includes the creation of new construction, road repair, and others. The type of garbage that caused, among others, wood, steel, and concrete. In addition, Agricultural activities also generate this type of garbage, among others, the rest of the food is rotten and the rest of the farm.

FIGURE 1. Scheme community empowerment in waste management

According to Rizal (2011) trash can be classified into several groups based on origin, namely;

1. Domestic Garbage, it comes from the neighborhoods or housing
2. Commercial Trash, it resulted from the environment trade activities such as shops, restaurants, restaurants, food stalls, markets, and supermarkets;
3. Industrial Waste, it is a by-product of this industrial activity strongly depends on the types of activities the industry itself;
4. Natural and other Junk, it can be either leaf, the rest of the natural disasters and so on.

2.3 Empowerment Garbage

Surabaya is the big city after Jakarta and Bandung which had problems with the handling of waste. The Mayor of Surabaya has already made a regulation which is quite ideal to tackle litter. Local regulations about waste management issued earlier, and it is less effective to tackle the problem of rubbish in Surabaya. Based on BPS data 384 city that raises the litter of 80,235.87 tons in a day, handling the garbage transported and dumped into the Landfills was of 4.2%, which burnt of 37.6%, which dumped into River 4.9% and no unhandled error of 53.3%. (Source: Department of hygiene and RTH Surabaya).

FIGURE 2. Volume of waste in Surabaya

Empowering the community in tackling the problems of waste management are planned and structured is one of the common approaches to do in the area. This is in line with the observations Nurhidayah (2017) that there are 3 stages to execute the community empowerment in waste management. These three stages are (1) the establishment of the Executive Board; (2) the Division of performance and (3) technical community participation. From some of the ideas in the empowerment of the garbage in the city of Surabaya using the approach by relying on Bank system waste and landfill in its management.

3. Reasearch Methods

The research was conducted using a descriptive qualitative approach. Qualitative research is research that his findings could not be completed through the exchange of statistical procedures as well as ways of quantifying (the matter of) other (Leksono, 2013). This research is a descriptive analysis of this type of research, i.e. research that seeks to explain or describe events that occur on objects of research in the later described, analyzed, and presented in such a way, so being a systematic overview (Suharto, 2004). Types of data used in this research are secondary data. Secondary data is data that is already available and collected by other parties. Because the data used are secondary data, data collection techniques used in the search techniques through direct contact. According to kuncoro (2009), It is the search data through direct contact is the researchers use computer terminals and can search for the required data directly. The technique of sports data using qualitative descriptive patterns. Is a descriptive qualitative data processing to a behavior, phenomena, events, problems, or certain circumstances which became the object of investigation the results of his findings in the form of meaningful sentence blurb that describes a certain understanding (Leksono, 2013).

In this study, the method of data collection used a qualitative approach and through direct contact. The qualitative approach in the form of interviews and observations. For secondary data types, data collection techniques used are search techniques for data through direct contact. Data processing technique in this paper uses qualitative descriptive patterns. The pattern is a descriptive qualitative data processing to a behavior, phenomena, events, issues or circumstances, which became the object of investigation the results of his findings in the form of meaningful sentence blurb that describes a certain understanding.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 An Overview Of Waste The City Of Surabaya

The city of Surabaya is a metropolitan city after the capital city of Jakarta, as well as the capital of East Java province. The city of Surabaya is famous as the largest city in Indonesia with a population of 2.9 million in the year 2016 (BPS Surabaya 2016). Therefore, it is relatively a lot of implications for the production of garbage in a year. Department of Hygiene of green open spaces (DHGOS) Surabaya city mentions that in 2016 the amount of garbage in Surabaya as much as 1,500 tons. Surabaya local Government already seeking in tackling the problem. One of the indicators that can describe a lot of garbage in the city of Surabaya is volume the amount of garbage over the years either inorganic or organic waste. Nowadays, the amount of organic waste is to reach 60% and 40% inorganic in Surabaya during the period 2014-2017 indicate trends fluctuating. According to data from the Department of Hygiene and health of the city of Surabaya, the amount of garbage was recorded in the city of Surabaya in the year 2014 reached 1,400 tons of garbage, while in 2015 rising to become 2000 tons, and in 2016 dropped back into 1,600 tons.

Figure 3. Volume of Garbage and Type of Waste (Source BPS Surabaya)

4.2 Waste management in Surabaya

The addition of the volume of garbage continues to grow every year. It making the government in Surabaya had to find a solution. In this case, the enforcement of the Bank's efforts in tackling the waste into the trash the city of Surabaya. In such situations, the Bank could be expected Trash the best solutions in waste management in the city. However, during the passage of the Bank Trash has not been fully resolved the problem. Because of the buildup of trash in the Waste Bank add to the problems in waste management efforts. In general the contributions of the Waste Bank did not effective yet role in waste management. The problem is in the city of Surabaya, there are only 3 places the end of the process (landfill) which is actively operates. However, during 3 years, the amount of garbage grew.

Routine activities done during this Waste Bank only place garbage collection from costumers. The remaining waste is not managed the Bank's Waste, so it will eventually be collected in the landfill. The role of the Waste Bank is getting obstruc cause difficulties to conduct waste management properly. In the end, the Waste Bank will not operate anymore, because of the litter build up that is not managed to cause problems. In addition, not only the Waste Bank but also approach 3R (Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle) have been also done by the Government. Recycling is the process of processing the returned goods are considered already has no economic value again through physical or chemical processes or both. Thus it obtained a product that can be used or traded. Recycling (recycle) waste can be differentiated into four ways namely primary recycling, the recycling of secondary, tertiary recycling and recycling quarter (Purwaningrum, 2016).

Figure 4. Scheme of waste management in Surabaya

4.3 The mechanism uses Rongsokanku.com In waste management city of Surabaya for the welfare of the community.

Rongsokanku.com is the online platform based e-marketing which is intended as a means of promotion and marketing of waste management either pre or post recycle. Rongsokanku.com acts as a community empowerment programs innovation of community the previously associated more done

face-to-face and not sustainable. Rongsokanku.com used the smart method of trading that focused empowerment management trash in the societies, in this case, the offender Manager while users with e-based marketing through website platform that can connect sellers with buyers. The process of trading until the transaction is conducted online through those pages. Rongsokanku.com will team up with Waste Bank and creative industries to get the data Bank's Waste and recycling that perpetrators would be a target of empowerment, cooperation also in the form of training and marketing with Rongsokanku.com before entering directly into the world of Trading. The customer and the perpetrators of the recycling already received training. It was given access to the use of the Rongsokanku.com, and it is connected to the world of trading which will become a place of promotion and marketing. While customers and principals of recycling already recorded or wishing to obtain facilities Rongsokanku.com and then register online on the page that has been provided and was able to enjoy the service.

The training program will run from 1 month to each Member Rongsokanku.com. The explanation of the material and the training is done through the website by the respective Chairman of the community. Thus, it is not just the waste management are getting better, but also provide employment to improve the welfare of life supported the existence of real mutual interactions participates in waste reduction efforts in so can encourage an interest in entrepreneurship. Rongsokanku.com is referred to as trading smart innovations, namely the incorporation of learning systems and e-marketing enables giving facilities the two parties (the Waste Bank and creative industries) are equally striving in waste management in real terms and increased access to finance for customers and industry peers.

4.4 The registration process At Rongsokanku.com

At front page web Rongsokanku.com contains features the introduction of Rongsokanku.com, easy steps to recognize the work system Rongsokanku.com and info product sales. There is also a menu list for customers who are interested in following the program. as well as the menu entry to the system for those who already have a good Bank account as well as the perpetrators of the Recycling Bins. At this stage the Bank's Waste and recycling industries do list at Rongsokanku.com by filling the platform data has been provided on the page Rongsokanku.com. After that, they will receive the registration verification through the no cell phone that has been filled in. The next stage i.e. does log in by using the same name at the time of registration and the password has been entered before.

FIGURE 5. Process Source: Author's Illustrations

4.5 Rongsokanku.com Important Applied Bank Trash and Recycling Industry Manager city of Surabaya to enhance the welfare of society

To face of the industrial revolution 4.0, Surabaya has a great opportunity to be able to benefit from the implementation of Rongsokanku.com for improving the well-being of the community with an effective waste management methods with innovative ways. There is no great need to fund budgeted for managing garbage Surabaya which became a source of welfare society of Surabaya. Simply by mastering information and communication technology, then the Surabaya can address the problem of waste management with good and true. The Bank's Waste and recycling industries the majority do not have a background in higher education. Most of them only as primary and secondary school graduates first. Consequently, they are hard to follow the development of information technology to solve a variety of problems. Perhaps, could still use some help from their children or people who are more eloquent but will be much better when they know themselves for personal activities. So that it can increase the level of modernity the Bank's trash and recycling industries. Therefore, Rongsokanku.com is present to

provide solutions in employee administration more sophisticated garbage in the midst of the development of the industrial revolution. This makes the program through Waste Bank and recycling industries Surabaya which have a level of understanding of the technology as well. In addition, it can increase societies welfare level and improve the environment healthier. When the customers and the creative business entrepreneurship of the recycling industry benefited economically and socially, then the existence of the waste can be managed and utilized, so that it can bring up a smarter regeneration in managing waste, and can eventually reduce the number of unemployment in Surabaya.

5. Conclusions and Suggestisons

5.1 Conclusions

Waste management method is still one of the obstacles faced by the Bank trash, recycling, industry offender nor the city government of Surabaya. Solutions to these problems, namely waste management innovations in Surabaya city accompanied by granting facilities access marketing recycled or waste recycling container with not capable to reach all elements of society online smart marketing-based like Rongsokanku.com. Rongsokanku.com expected to be a means of managing and marketing a sustainable waste and is able to provide the independence effort for all elements of society in the future.

5.2 Suggestisons

To support the improvement of waste management in the city of Surabaya, Governments also need to innovate along with the determination of the environmental maintenance regulations. Implementation of the innovation can be done hand in hand with innovations developed by Nations such as the existence of online innovation in the form of Rongsokanku.com. In addition, the most important thing i.e. awareness throughout the community about waste management elements well and wisely so that it was able to realize a good environment and improving their well-being.

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